

Molecular dynamic simulation studies of thermal diffusion of lithium and lithium based alloys

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Abstract

Lithium and Lithium based alloys are widely used in the industry as an important source of renewable energy, for example, battery electrolytes, electrodes and catalysts. Despite huge research activities in past several decades, a detailed kinematic study of Li-ion within the material and the structural stability of the material are still lacking in the literature. Here we present a detailed study of the thermal diffusion of Li and Li₂O using molecular dynamic simulations software LAMMPS (1,2). Velocity verlet scheme is used for the time advancement of the system. Temperature dependence of diffusion coefficients D(T) for Li and Li₂O were computed. Activation energies (E_a) for both the material were determined using the Arrhenius relation $D=D_0e^{-E_a/KT}$. The obtained results are consistent with previous experimental and numerical observations (2,3). Furthermore, we create vacancies at the Li sites and investigate the role of the concentration of vacancies on the thermal transport of the material.

Thermal diffusion, Molecular dynamic simulation, Activation energy, Defects

References

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